

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Camilla Svendsen

Your email address: camilla.svendsen@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 10 01 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

None

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I work with evidence-based chemical risk assessment, the current paradigm-shift in toxicology calls for use of NAMs in these assessments. I am therefore interested in the development of tools to be able to use NAMs, including in vitro tests, in these assessments.

Signature

Notes

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Declaration of Contributor Interests

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form.

Personal details

Your name: Paul Whaley

Your email address, for contact purposes: paul@whaleyresearch.uk

Date of completion of this form (DD MMM YYYY): 3 February 2023

Contribution to the Research Project

Conceptualisation, methodology, writing - original draft, writing - review and editing, visualisation, supervision

Interests

Place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the SR?		Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially conflict with the objectives of the SR?	
X	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.		Deeply held beliefs or convictions
	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	x	Current and previous research findings or projects
	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.	x	Commitments to specific standards or processes
	From litigation or legal cases		Publicly held positions
	From grants		Personal relationships
	Other financial interests	x	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
		x	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
			Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I have or am providing consultancy services for: the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC) at Johns Hopkins University Bloomberg School of Public Health; Lancaster University, mainly around securing impact of the research I was doing for my PhD (completed 2020); and for Yordas Group, to deliver training in SR methods for EU JRC. I also receive an Honorarium as Editor in Chief for the journal *Evidence-Based Toxicology* (EBT), to which this manuscript is being submitted. I am setting up the Institute for Evidence-Based Toxicology, a non-profit company based in Germany. The company will begin trading in 2023, and I am one of 4 Directors with a 25% share in the business. The work of the company will be providing services relating to evidence-based methods in toxicology and environmental health.

In general, my consultancy work is around development and promotion of systematic review methods in environmental health research, delivering training around these methods, and providing editorial services. While relevant to the present work, I am not aware of any way in which these interests could compromise the integrity of the research I am undertaking here.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I have a general public commitment to high quality systematic review methods in support of environmental health policy and decision-making, and am actively involved in a range of projects intended to improve research standards in evidence synthesis. I have developed conduct standards (e.g. COSTER), reporting checklists (e.g. ROSES), and critical appraisal tools (e.g. CREST_Triage, PRIVAT) to support the production of high quality systematic reviews and evidence maps. I am an active member of the GRADE Working Group, an informal UK NGO network promoting good environmental policy in the UK, have a senior role at EBTC that involves promoting SR and other evidence-based methods in toxicology and environmental health; similarly, my role at the journal EBT involves high-profile public advocacy for evidence-based approaches to evidence synthesis that includes advocating for the use of study appraisal instruments, of which the present manuscript is an example. In general, I have a strong interest in supporting precautionary, evidence-based approaches to environmental health policy. While relevant to the present work, I am not aware of any way in which these interests could compromise the integrity of the research I am undertaking here, as the standards implied by the work are consistent with those to which I have expressed public commitment.

Signature

SIGNED

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Gunn Elisabeth Vist

Your email address: gunn.vist@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 12 Jan 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Data curation, Writing-Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

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Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I have no financial interests related to this publication

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am convinced of the benefits of being evidence-based in research. Otherwise, no conflicting interests pertaining to this publication

Signature

Gunn E Vist

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Trine Husøy

Your email address: trine.husoy@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 10 01 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualisation, methodology, writing – review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

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Non to declare

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Work at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health as a senior scientist in the area of food safety, including risk assessment of chemicals and systematic reviews.

Expert in the panel for food additives and flavourings (FAF) panel of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

Chair of the Panel of Food additives, flavourings, processing aids, materials in contact with food and cosmetics in the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment performing risk assessment using systematic methods.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Trine Husøy". The signature is written in a cursive, slightly slanted style.

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Anna Beronius

Your email address: anna.beronius@ki.se

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 13 Jan 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Review and comment

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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N/A

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Beronius is one of the initiators and developers of the SciRAP tools for data appraisal, which includes a tool for evaluating quality of in vitro toxicity data.

Signature

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This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Emma Di Consiglio

Your email address: emma.diconsiglio@iss.it

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):09 01 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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The issues described in the paper partially overlap and/or are extremely useful for other projects and/or risk assessment activities (EFSA WG, EU COM), in which I am actively involved, related to the use and development of NAMs.

Signature

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Your name: Ingrid L. Druwe

Your email address: druwe.ingrid@epa.gov

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 01/14/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing- Reviewing and Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "J. Drane". The signature is written in a cursive style with a large initial "J" and "D".

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Thomas Hartung

Your email address: THartun1@jhu.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 09 Jan 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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Insert here

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As Chair for Evidence-based Toxicology at Johns Hopkins University and former head of the European Centre for the Validation of Alternative Methods, the project touches on fundamental beliefs and foundations of my work.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'A. Maby', is written over a light blue horizontal line.

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Vasiliki I. Hatzi

Your email address: v.hatzi@bpi.gr

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 13/01/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

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Interest in highlighting the usefulness of in vitro studies and contribute in the global attempt to eliminate the use of in vivo studies in chemicals testing; in providing the knowledge from the laboratory research field of cytogenetics, for the creation of a useful tool for applied and regulatory sciences; and in evolving personally and professionally through interesting collaborations with creative people.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "B. Xar/in". The signature is written in a cursive style and is underlined with a single horizontal stroke.

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Sebastian Hoffmann

Your email address: Sebastian.hoffmann@seh-cs.com

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 09 01 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing; Supervision

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

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not applicable

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

not applicable

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sebastian', followed by a stylized flourish.

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
- (2) Contributors to a research project should declare any interests that a reasonable person would want to be aware of, in order to be confident that all relevant interests are known and can be evaluated for their potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in the project.
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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Carlijn Hooijmans

Your email address: Carlijn.hooijmans@radboudumc.nl

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):11012023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Advice on systematic review and study design methods

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I do not have any of the listed non financial interests. I am a scientist at the Radboud university of Nijmegen in the Netherlands, and I run the meta research team. A team that focusses on developing, applying and disseminating systematic review methodology across evidence streams, performing meta-research on research rigour and robustness principles and providing education within and beyond the Radboudumc.

Signature

A handwritten signature consisting of a stylized, scribbled initial followed by the name "Guymans" written in a cursive, handwritten style.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Georges Kass

Your email address: georges.kass@efsa.europa.eu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 10/01/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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<input type="checkbox"/> From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/> Other financial interests	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am working for the European Food Authority, an EU delocalised agency of the EC. However, any publication co-authored by me will carry a disclaimer that the views presented may not necessarily represent the views of my organisation.

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of a series of fluid, overlapping strokes that form a stylized, somewhat abstract shape.

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Kyriaki Machera

Your email address: k.machera@bpi.gr

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):16.01.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
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<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

No financial interests.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

This journal paper/work falls under my current and previous scientific interests and projects.

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Andy', written in a cursive style.

Notes

(1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Joshua F. Robinson

Your email address: joshua.robinson@ucsf.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 10 Jan 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
<input type="checkbox"/> From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> Deeply held beliefs or convictions
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<input type="checkbox"/> From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal relationships
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other financial interests	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Publication will improve my professional standing as an academic researcher which could lead to increased financial benefit. A major metric of academic job performance is the quality and number of publications that I associated with. Serving as a consultant for this group and

publishing our results will increase visibility of my research expertise in the area of toxicology.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am providing my expertise in the areas of toxicology and in vitro science. My knowledge and views are based on specific training and experience which I will provide to the group. I am greatly interested in the use and applicability of new approach methodologies (e.g., in vitro, in silico approaches) in chemical hazard and risk assessment. I serve on council of the Society of Birth Defects Research and Prevention, which is also greatly interested in these research areas.

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'JFR', written over a light blue horizontal line.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Erwin L Roggen

Your email address: elro@3rsmc.onmicrosoft.com

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 22.05.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

"Protocol for designing INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies"

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?		Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?	
no	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.	no	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
no	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	no	Current and previous research findings or projects
no	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.	no	Commitments to specific standards or processes
no	From litigation or legal cases	no	Publicly held positions
no	From grants	no	Personal relationships
none	Other financial interests	no	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
		no	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
		no	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

No financial interests

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

No non-financial interests

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'D. J. P.', written over a horizontal line.

Notes

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Handwritten initials 'CR' in blue ink.

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Andrew A. Rooney

Your email address: andrew.rooney@nih.gov

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 20 Jan 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Supervision; Writing – review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

No financial interests as indicated by lack of "X" above.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

One non-financial interest as indicated by "X" above as I am employed in the National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) in the National Institute of Health (NIH) of the United States of America. I am the Chief (acting) of the Integrative Health Assessments Branch of the Division of Translational Toxicology in the U.S. NIEHS in the NIH. The views expressed are my own and do not necessarily represent the views or policies of the U.S. National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'C. J. Y.', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Nicolas Roth

Your email address: nicolas.roth@unibas.ch

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 21.05.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

None

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am an Associate Editor of systematic reviews and systematic evidence maps at Environment International – I have an interest in developing tools, instruments, methods and standards that contribute to advance best practice in the field.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'N. J. M.', written in a cursive style.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Eliana Spilioti

Your email address: e.spilioti@bpi.gr

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):13.01.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

No financial interests.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

This journal paper/work falls under my current and previous scientific interests and projects.

Signature

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Anastasia Spyropoulou

Your email address: a.spyropoulou@bpi.gr

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):13.01.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

No financial interests.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

This journal paper/work falls under my current and previous scientific interests and projects.

Signature

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Olga Tcheremenskaia

Your email address: olga.tcheremenskaia@iss.it

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 09/01/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
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Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Being involved in several institutional activities and projects under OECD (on AOP, IATA, in silico NAMs) that aim to increase the confidence in NAMs with the purpose of using them in risk assessment procedures, the issues described in the papers partially overlap with my other interests and are of great interest for my current work.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Olga Tcheumina". The signature is written in a cursive style with a large initial 'O'.

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
- (2) Contributors to a research project should declare any interests that a reasonable person would want to be aware of, in order to be confident that all relevant interests are known and can be evaluated for their potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in the project.
- (3) It is unlikely that someone with no interests in relation to a project would still be interested in being involved in a project. Declaring no interests is therefore unlikely to be a valid response to the questions in this form.
- (4) Interests that cannot contractually be declared need not be described in detail, but their existence must be noted. If the contract specifies that not even the presence of a contractual limitation can be declared, the contributor should state they are unable to complete the form.

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Emanuela Testai

Your email address: emanuela.testai@iss.it

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):09/01/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing; Funding acquisition

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Being involved in other projects using in vitro systems and NAMs, as well as in risk assessment procedures issues described in the papers partially overlap and or are extremely useful for my current work

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Emanuele Cresto". The signature is written in a cursive style with a distinct loop at the end of the last name.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Mathieu Vinken

Your email address: mathieu.vinken@vub.be

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 09/01/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptual input for set-up of the study

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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<input type="checkbox"/> From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/> Other financial interests	<input type="checkbox"/> Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

None

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

None

Signature

A handwritten signature consisting of a vertical line on the right, a horizontal line crossing it, and a loop on the left side.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Gro Haarklou Mathisen

Your email address: gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 17 January 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, data curation, methodology, visualisation

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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Non-financial interests

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

None

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Evidence-based chemical risk assessments are a large part of my daily work. As the toxicity data are shifting from animal studies to NAMs, I am interested in the development of tools for incorporation of such data as evidence in chemical risk assessments.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Gro Harlem Brundtland". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

Notes

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